

Computable Separation in Topology, from T_0 to T_2

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Abstract: This article continues the study of computable elementary topology started in [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009]. For computable topological spaces we introduce a number of computable versions of the topological separation axioms T_0 , T_1 and T_2 . The axioms form an implication chain with many equivalences. By counterexamples we show that most of the remaining implications are proper. In particular, it turns out that computable T_1 is equivalent to computable T_2 and that for spaces without isolated points the hierarchy collapses, that is, the weakest computable T_0 axiom WCT_0 is equivalent to the strongest computable T_2 axiom SCT_2 . The SCT_2 -spaces are closed under Cartesian product, this is not true for most of the other classes of spaces. Finally we show that the computable version of a basic axiom for an effective topology in intuitionistic topology is equivalent to SCT_2 .

Key Words: computable analysis, computable topology, axioms of separation

Category: F.0, F.m, G.0, G.m

1 Introduction

This article continues with the study of computable topology started in [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009]. For computable topological spaces (as defined in [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009]) we define a number of computable versions of the topological T_0 -, T_1 - and T_2 -axioms and study their relation. We will use the notation and results from [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009] some of which are mentioned very shortly in Section 2.

In Section 3 we introduce a number of axioms for computable separation of points in T_0 -, T_1 - and T_2 -spaces. We show that the axioms are logically equivalent for equivalent computable topological spaces, where two computable topological spaces are equivalent, if they induce the same computability on the points [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 21].

In Section 4 we prove all the implications between these axioms. They form a linear hierarchy with several equivalences. Surprisingly, computable T_1 and computable T_2 are equivalent. The hierarchy collapses for spaces with no singleton open sets. We characterize the strongest axiom SCT_2 and give a sufficient condition for it.

In Section 5 we give counterexamples for all the implications introduced in Section 4 that are proper.

For T_2 -spaces also compact sets can be separated by open neighborhoods. In Section 6 we define some computable versions of separating compact sets and

study their relation. We also introduce the computable version IT of a basic separation axiom from intuitionistic topology and prove $\text{IT} \iff \text{SCT}_2$.

If some of the introduced axioms holds for a computable topological space then it also holds for every subspace. The strongly computable T_2 -spaces are closed under Cartesian product, this is not true for most of the other axioms. This is shown in Section 7.

Some computable separation axioms have been used in [Schröder 1998, Grubba et al. 2007, Grubba et al. 2007, Xu and Grubba 2009], where, however, for a computable topological space the basis sets must be non-empty. Some results of this article have already been proved (as weaker versions) in [Grubba et al. 2007, Xu and Grubba 2009].

2 Preliminaries

We will use the terminology and abbreviations summarized in [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Section 2] and also results from [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009]. For further details see [Weihrauch 2000, Weihrauch 2008, Brattka et al. 2008].

By Σ we denote a sufficiently large finite alphabet such that $0, 1 \in \Sigma$. As usual, Σ^* is the set of finite words and Σ^ω is the set of infinite sequences of symbols from Σ . Let Σ be a finite alphabet such that $0, 1 \in \Sigma$. By Σ^* we denote the set of finite words over Σ and by Σ^ω the set of infinite sequences $p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \Sigma$ over Σ , $p = (p(0)p(1)\dots)$. For a word $w \in \Sigma^*$ let $|w|$ be its length and let $\varepsilon \in \Sigma^*$ be the empty word. For $p \in \Sigma^\omega$ let $p^{<i} \in \Sigma^*$ be the prefix of p of length $i \in \mathbb{N}$. We use the “wrapping function” $\iota : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$, $\iota(a_1a_2\dots a_k) := 110a_10a_20\dots a_k011$ for coding words such that $\iota(u)$ and $\iota(v)$ cannot overlap properly. Let $\langle i, j \rangle := (i+j)(i+j+1)/2+j$ be the bijective Cantor pairing function on \mathbb{N} . We consider standard functions for finite or countable tupling on Σ^* and Σ^ω denoted by $\langle \cdot \rangle$ [Weihrauch 2000, Definition 2.1.7], in particular, $\langle u_1, \dots, u_n \rangle = \iota(u_1)\dots\iota(u_n)$, $\langle u, p \rangle = \iota(u)p$, $\langle p, q \rangle = (p(0)q(0)p(1)q(1)\dots)$ and $\langle p_0, p_1, \dots \rangle \langle i, j \rangle = p_i(j)$ for $u, u_1, u_2, \dots \in \Sigma^*$ and $p, q, p_0, p_1, \dots \in \Sigma^\omega$. For $u \in \Sigma^*$ and $w \in \Sigma^* \cup \Sigma^\omega$ let $u \ll w$ iff $\iota(u)$ is a subword of w and let \hat{w} be the longest subword $v \in 11\Sigma^*11$ of w (and the empty word if no such subword exists). Then for $u, w_1, w_2 \in \Sigma^*$, $(u \ll w_1 \vee u \ll w_2) \iff u \ll \hat{w}_1\hat{w}_2$.

For $Y_0, \dots, Y_n \in \{\Sigma^*, \Sigma^\omega\}$ a partial function $f : \subseteq Y_1 \times \dots \times Y_n \rightarrow Y_0$ is computable, if it is computed by a Type-2 machine. A Type-2 machine M is a Turing machine with n input tapes, one output tape and finitely many additional work tapes. A specification assigns to the input tapes $1, \dots, n$ and the output tape 0 types $Y_i \in \{\Sigma^*, \Sigma^\omega\}$ such that the machine computes a function $f_M : \subseteq Y_1 \times \dots \times Y_n \rightarrow Y_0$ [Weihrauch 2000]. Notice that on the output tape the machine can only write and move its head to the right.

A notation of a set X is a surjective partial function $\nu : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow X$ and a representation is a surjective partial function $\delta : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow X$. Here, finite or infinite sequences of symbols are considered as “concrete names” of the “abstract” elements of X . Computability on X is defined by computations on names. Let $\gamma_i : \subseteq Y_i \rightarrow X_i$, $Y_i \in \{\Sigma^*, \Sigma^\omega\}$ for $i \in \{0, 1\}$ be notations or representations. A set $W \subseteq X_0$ is called γ_0 -r.e. (recursively enumerable), if there is a Type-2 machine M that halts on input $y_0 \in \text{dom}(\gamma_0)$ iff $\gamma_0(y_0) \in W$. A function $h : \subseteq Y_1 \rightarrow Y_0$ realizes a multi-function $f : X_1 \rightrightarrows X_0$, iff $\gamma_0 \circ h(y_1) \in f \circ \gamma_1(y_1)$ whenever $f \circ \gamma_1(y_1) \neq \emptyset$. The function f is called (γ_1, γ_0) -computable, if it has a computable realization. The definitions can be generalized straightforwardly to subsets of $X_1 \times \dots \times X_n$ and multi-functions $f : X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow X_0$ ($(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n)$ -r.e., $(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n, \gamma_0)$ -computable).

In this article we study axioms of computable separation for *computable topological spaces* $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 4], where τ is a T_0 -topology on the set X and $\nu : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow \beta$ is a notation of a base β of τ such that $\text{dom}(\nu)$ is recursive and there is an r.e. set $S \subseteq (\text{dom}(\nu))^3$ such that $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \bigcup \{\nu(w) \mid (u, v, w) \in S\}$. We mention expressly that in the past various spaces have been called “computable topological space”. We allow $U = \emptyset$ for $U \in \beta$ which is forbidden in, for example, [Grubba et al. 2007, Xu and Grubba 2009].

We define a notation ν^{fs} of the finite subsets of the base β by $\nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = W : \iff ((\forall v \ll w) v \in \text{dom}(\nu) \wedge W = \{\nu(v) \mid v \ll w\})$. Then $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}$ and $\bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}$ are notations of the finite unions and the finite intersections of base elements, respectively.

For the points of X we consider the canonical (or inner) representation $\delta : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow X$; $\delta(p) = x$ iff p is a list of all $\iota(u)$ (possibly padded with 1s) such that $x \in \nu(u)$. For the set of open sets, the topology τ we consider the inner representation $\theta : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \tau$ defined by $u \in \text{dom}(\nu)$ if $u \ll p \in \text{dom}(\theta)$ and $\delta(p) := \bigcup \{\nu(u) \mid u \ll p\}$. For the closed sets we consider the outer representation $\psi^-(p) := X \setminus \theta(p)$. Finally, for the set of compact sets (of T_2 -spaces we consider the cover representation defined by $u \in \text{dom}(\nu^{\text{fs}})$ if $u \ll p \in \text{dom}(\kappa)$ and $\kappa(p) = K$ iff p is a list of all $\iota(u)$ such that $K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u)$ [Weihrauch 2000, Weihrauch and Grubba 2009].

3 Axioms for Computable Separation of Points

For a topological space $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau)$ we consider the following separation properties:

Definition 1 (classical separation axioms).

$$T_0 : (\forall x, y \in X, x \neq y)(\exists W \in \tau)((x \in W \wedge y \notin W) \vee (x \notin W \wedge y \in W)),$$

$$T_1 : (\forall x, y \in X, x \neq y)(\exists W \in \tau)(x \in W \wedge y \notin W),$$

$$T_2 : (\forall x, y \in X, x \neq y)(\exists U, V \in \tau)(U \cap V = \emptyset \wedge x \in U \wedge y \in V).$$

For $i = 0, 1, 2$, we call $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau)$ a T_i -space iff T_i is true. Obviously, $T_2 \implies T_1 \implies T_0$, where the implications are proper [Engelking 1989]. T_2 -spaces are called *Hausdorff spaces*. We mention that (X, τ) is a T_1 -space, iff all sets $\{x\}$ ($x \in X$) are closed [Engelking 1989].

In this article we study computable topological spaces $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$, which by definition are T_0 -spaces with countable base (also called *second countable T_0 -spaces*). First, we introduce computable versions CT_i of the conditions T_i by requiring that the existing open neighborhoods can be computed. For the points we compute basic neighborhoods (see Lemma 4.1 below).

Definition 2 (axioms of computable separation). For $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ define conditions CT_i as follows.

CT_0 : The multi-function t_0 is (δ, δ, ν) -computable where t_0 maps every $(x, y) \in X^2$ such that $x \neq y$ to some $U \in \beta$ such that

$$(x \in U \text{ and } y \notin U) \text{ or } (x \notin U \text{ and } y \in U). \quad (1)$$

CT_1 : The multi-function t_1 is (δ, δ, ν) -computable, where t_1 maps every $(x, y) \in X^2$ such that $x \neq y$ to some $U \in \beta$ such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$.

CT_2 : The multi-function t_2 is $(\delta, \delta, [\nu, \nu])$ -computable, where t_2 maps every $(x, y) \in X^2$ such that $x \neq y$ to some $(U, V) \in \beta^2$ such that $U \cap V = \emptyset$, $x \in U$ and $y \in V$.

Obviously, CT_i implies T_i . We introduce some further computable T_i -conditions.

Definition 3 (further axioms of computable separation).

WCT_0 : There is an r.e. set $H \subseteq \text{dom}(\nu) \times \text{dom}(\nu)$ such that

$$(\forall x, y, x \neq y)(\exists (u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)) \text{ and} \quad (2)$$

$$(\forall (u, v) \in H) \begin{cases} \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset \\ \vee (\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v) \\ \vee (\exists y) \nu(v) = \{y\} \subseteq \nu(u). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

SCT_0 : The multi-function t_0^s is $(\delta, \delta, [\nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \nu])$ -computable where t_0^s maps every $(x, y) \in X^2$ such that $x \neq y$ to some $(k, U) \in \mathbb{N} \times \beta$ such that $(k = 1, x \in U \text{ and } y \notin U) \text{ or } (k = 2, x \notin U \text{ and } y \in U)$.

CT'_0 : There is an r.e. set $H \subseteq \text{dom}(\nu_{\mathbb{N}}) \times \text{dom}(\nu) \times \text{dom}(\nu)$ such that

$$(\forall x, y, x \neq y)(\exists(w, u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)) \quad \text{and} \quad (4)$$

$$(\forall(w, u, v) \in H) \begin{cases} \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset \\ \vee \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1 \wedge (\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v) \\ \vee \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 2 \wedge (\exists y) \nu(v) = \{y\} \subseteq \nu(u). \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

CT'_1 : There is an r.e. set $H \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that

$$(\forall x, y, x \neq y)(\exists(u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)) \quad \text{and} \quad (6)$$

$$(\forall(u, v) \in H) \begin{cases} \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset \\ \vee (\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v). \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

CT'_2 : There is an r.e. set $H \in \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that

$$(\forall x, y, x \neq y)(\exists(u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)) \quad \text{and} \quad (8)$$

$$(\forall(u, v) \in H) \begin{cases} \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset \\ \vee (\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} = \nu(v). \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

SCT_2 : There is an r.e. set $H \in \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that

$$(\forall x, y, x \neq y)(\exists(u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)) \quad \text{and} \quad (10)$$

$$(\forall(u, v) \in H) \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset. \quad (11)$$

We do not consider the numerous variants of the separation axioms where in some places the representations δ of the points, θ of the open sets and ψ^- of the closed sets are replaced by δ^- , θ^- and ψ^+ , respectively [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 5].

In contrast to CT_0 , in SCT_0 the separating function gives immediate information about the direction of the separation. Also in CT'_0 some information about the direction of the separation is included while no such information is given in the weak version WCT_0 . CT'_0 , CT'_1 and CT'_2 are versions of CT_0 , CT_1 and CT_2 , respectively where base sets are used instead of points (see Theorem 5 below). The strong version SCT_2 results from CT'_2 by excluding the case $(\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} = \nu(v)$. Notice that SCT_2 results also from WCT_0 , CT'_0 and CT'_1 by excluding the corresponding cases. The following examples illustrate the definitions. Further examples are given in Section 5.

Example 1. 1. (SCT_2) The *computable real line* is defined by $\mathbf{R} := (\mathbb{R}, \tau_{\mathbb{R}}, \beta, \nu)$ such that $\tau_{\mathbb{R}}$ is the real line topology and ν is a canonical notation of the set of all open intervals with rational endpoints. \mathbf{R} is a computable topological space. The set $H := \{(u, v) \mid \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset\}$ is r.e. Therefore the computable real line is an SCT_2 -space.

2. (T_0 but not WCT_0) The *computable lower real line* is defined by $\mathbf{R}_{<} := (\mathbb{R}, \tau_{<}, \beta_{<}, \nu_{<})$ where $\nu_{<}(w) := (\nu_{\mathbb{Q}}; \infty)$. $\mathbf{R}_{<}$ is T_0 but not T_1 . Suppose it is WCT_0 . Then by (3) $H = \emptyset$ since for any two base elements U and V , U is not a singleton and $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$. But $H \neq \emptyset$ by (2).

3. (CT_0 but not T_1) The Sierpinski space defined by $\mathbf{Si} := (\{\perp, \top\}, \tau_{\mathbf{Si}}, \beta_{\mathbf{Si}}, \nu_{\mathbf{Si}})$ such that $\nu_{\mathbf{Si}}(0) = \{\perp, \top\}$ and $\nu_{\mathbf{Si}}(1) = \{\top\}$. For $p, q \in \Sigma^\omega$ let $f(p, q) := 1 \in \Sigma^*$. Then f realizes t_0 since for $x \neq y$, $x \in \nu_{\mathbf{Si}}(1) \iff y \notin \nu_{\mathbf{Si}}(1)$.
4. (T_1 but not T_2 or WCT_0) Let $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbb{N}, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ such that $\tau = \beta$ is the set of cofinite subsets of \mathbb{N} and ν is a canonical notation of β . Then \mathbf{X} is a computable topological space. \mathbf{X} is T_1 since singletons $\{x\}$ are closed but not T_2 since the intersection of any two non-empty open sets is not empty. Suppose \mathbf{X} is WCT_0 . Then by (3) $H = \emptyset$ since for any two base elements U and V , U is not a singleton and $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$. But $H \neq \emptyset$ by (2).

By the next lemma, in the above computable separation axioms the notation ν of the base can be replaced by the representation θ of the open sets and the axioms are robust, that is, they do not depend on the notation ν of the base explicitly but only on the computability concept on the points induced by it [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 21, Theorem 22].

Lemma 4. 1. For $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ let \overline{CT}_i be the condition obtained from CT_i and let \overline{SCT}_0 be the condition obtained from SCT_0 by replacing β and ν by τ and θ , respectively. Then $\overline{CT}_i \iff CT_i$ and $\overline{SCT}_0 \iff SCT_0$.

2. Let $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = (X, \tau, \tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\nu})$ be a computable topological space equivalent to $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 21]. Then each separation axiom from Definitions 2 and 3 for \mathbf{X} is equivalent to the corresponding axiom for $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$.

Proof: 1. CT_i implies \overline{CT}_i since $\nu \leq \theta$. For the other direction observe that the multi-function $h : X \times \tau \rightrightarrows \beta$ such that $U \in h(x, W) \iff x \in U \subseteq W$ is (δ, θ, ν) -computable. The argument is valid also for SCT_0 .

2. Since \mathbf{X} and $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ are equivalent, there are computable functions $g, \tilde{g} : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^\omega$ such that $\nu(u) = \tilde{\theta} \circ g(u)$ and $\tilde{\nu}(u) = \theta \circ \tilde{g}(u)$. Furthermore, $\delta \equiv \tilde{\delta}$ and $\theta \equiv \tilde{\theta}$ by [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Theorem 22]. Since equivalent representations induce the same computability, $\overline{CT}_i \iff \overline{\tilde{CT}}_i$ and $\overline{SCT}_0 \iff \overline{\tilde{SCT}}_0$, hence by 1, $CT_i \iff \overline{\tilde{CT}}_i$ (for $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$) and $SCT_0 \iff \overline{\tilde{SCT}}_0$.

CT'_i for $i = 0, 1, 2$: Below we will prove $CT_i \iff CT'_i$. Apply 1. of this lemma.

WCT₀: Assume SCT_0 . Let $\tilde{H} := \{(\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}) \mid (\exists(u, v) \in H)(\tilde{u} \ll g(u) \wedge \tilde{v} \ll g(v))\}$. Then $\overline{\tilde{SCT}}_0$ can be shown straightforwardly. By symmetry, $\overline{\tilde{SCT}}_2 \implies SCT_2$.

SCT₂: Use the same argument as for WCT_0 . □

4 Implications

In this section we prove the implications between the separation properties, in the next section we prove by counterexamples that almost all the implications are proper.

Theorem 5.

1. $SCT_2 \implies CT_2 \implies CT_0 \implies WCT_0$,
2. $CT_2 \iff CT'_2 \iff CT_1 \iff CT'_1$,
3. $CT_0 \iff SCT_0 \iff CT'_0$,

Proof: $SCT_2 \implies CT_2 \implies CT_1 \implies SCT_0 \implies CT_0$: Straightforward.

$CT'_0 \implies WCT_0$: Straightforward.

$CT_0 \implies SCT_0$: The information whether $x \in U$ or whether $y \in U$ can be obtained from x, y and $U \in t_0(x, y)$. If $x \neq y$ then either $x \in U$ or $y \in U$. Since the relation “ $z \in U$ ” is (δ, ν) -r.e. we can answer the question by trying to prove $x \in U$ and $y \in U$ simultaneously.

$CT'_0 \implies SCT_0$: There is a machine that on input $(p, q) \in \Sigma^\omega \times \Sigma^\omega$ first searches for $(w, u, v) \in H$ such that $u \ll p$ and $v \ll q$ and then prints $\langle w, u \rangle$ if $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1$ and $\langle w, v \rangle$, otherwise. Then f_M realizes the function t_0 .

$SCT_0 \implies CT'_0$: By [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Theorem 11] there is a computable function $g : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^\omega$ such that $\bigcap \nu^{fs}(w) = \theta \circ g(w)$.

Let M be a machine realizing the multi-function t_0^s . There is a machine N that halts on input $(w, u, v) \in (\Sigma^*)^3$ if and only if there are words $r, s \in \text{dom}(\nu^{fs})$, some $u_1 \in \text{dom}(\nu)$ and some $t \leq \min(|r|, |s|)$ such that M on input $(r1^\omega, s1^\omega)$ halts in t steps with result $\langle w, u_1 \rangle$ and

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} u \ll g(\widehat{r}\iota(u_1)) \wedge v \ll g(s) \quad \text{if } \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1, \\ u \ll g(r) \wedge v \ll g(\widehat{s}\iota(u_1)) \quad \text{if } \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 2. \end{array} \right\}$$

Let $H := \text{dom}(f_N)$.

For showing (4) assume $\delta(p) = x \neq y = \delta(q)$. Then there are t, w, u_1 such that the machine M halts on input (p, q) in t steps with result $\langle w, u_1 \rangle$ such that either $(\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1, x \in \nu(u_1), y \notin \nu(u_1))$ or $(\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 2, x \notin \nu(u_1), y \in \nu(u_1))$. Suppose, $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1$. Let $r := p^{<t}$ and $s := q^{<t}$. Then M also on input $(r1^\omega, s1^\omega)$ halts in t steps with result $\langle w, u_1 \rangle$. Since $\delta(p) = x, x \in \nu(u_1)$ and $\delta(q) = y, x \in \bigcap \nu^{fs}(\widehat{r}\iota(u_1))$ and $y \in \bigcap \nu^{fs}(s)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Section 2 and Lemma 10], hence there are u, v such that $u \ll g(\widehat{r}\iota(u_1)), x \in \nu(u), v \ll g(s)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$. Therefore, there is some $(w, u, v) \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$. The argument is similar for $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 2$. Thus (4) is proved.

For showing (5) let

$$(w, u, v) \in H, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1, x \in \nu(u), y \in \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) \text{ and } x \neq y.$$

By the definition of H there are r, s, t and u_1 such that $t \leq \min(|r|, |s|)$ and M on input $(r1^\omega, s1^\omega)$ halts in t steps with result $\langle w, u_1 \rangle$ and $u \ll g(\hat{r} \iota(u_1))$ and $v \ll g(s)$. Therefore, $x \in \nu(u) \subseteq \delta[r\Sigma^\omega] \cap \nu(u_1)$ and $y \in \nu(v) \subseteq \delta[s\Sigma^\omega]$. By (SCT₀), $x \in \nu(u_1)$ and $y \notin \nu(u_1)$. On the other hand, $y \in \nu(u) \subseteq \nu(u_1)$ (contradiction). Therefore, if $(w, u, v) \in H$, $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1$, $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(u) \cap \nu(v)$, then $x = y$, hence,

$$((w, u, v) \in H, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1 \text{ and } \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) \neq \emptyset) \implies (\exists x) \nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v).$$

This shows (5) for the case $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1$. For the case $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 2$ the argument is similar.

CT₁ \iff **CT'₁**: This is the special case of **SCT₀** \iff **CT'₀** where $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w) = 1$ in all cases.

CT'₂ \implies **CT₂**: Let M be a machine which on input (p, q) searches for some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $u \ll p$ and $v \ll q$ and writes $\langle u, v \rangle$ if the search is successful and diverges otherwise. Suppose $\delta(p) = x \neq y = \delta(q)$. By (8) on input (p, q) the machine M finds some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v)$. By (9), $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset$. Therefore, f_M realizes t_2 .

CT'₁ \implies **CT'₂**: Assume **CT'₁**. Since \mathbf{X} is a computable topological space, there is a computable function g such that $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset \circ g(u, v)$. Let H be the r.e. set from **CT'₁**. Let

$$H_2 := \{(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) \mid \bar{u} \ll g(u, v'), \bar{v} \ll g(u', v) \text{ for some } (u, v), (u', v') \in H\}.$$

H_2 is r.e since H is r.e. We prove (8) and (9) for H_2 .

Suppose $x \neq y$. By (6) there are $(u, v), (u', v') \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u)$, $y \in \nu(v)$, $y \in \nu(u')$ and $x \in \nu(v')$. Since $x \in \nu(u) \cap \nu(v')$ and $y \in \nu(u') \cap \nu(v)$, there is some $(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) \in H_2$ such that $x \in \nu(\bar{u})$ and $y \in \nu(\bar{v})$. Therefore, (8) holds for H_2 .

Suppose $(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) \in H_2$ and $\nu(\bar{u}) \cap \nu(\bar{v}) \neq \emptyset$. Then there are $(u, v), (u', v') \in H$ such that $\nu(\bar{u}) \subseteq \nu(u) \cap \nu(v')$ and $\nu(\bar{v}) \subseteq \nu(u') \cap \nu(v)$. Since $\nu(\bar{u}) \cap \nu(\bar{v}) \neq \emptyset$, $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) \neq \emptyset$ and $\nu(u') \cap \nu(v) \neq \emptyset$. By (7) for some $x, y \in X$, $\nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v)$ and $\nu(u') = \{y\} \subseteq \nu(v')$, hence $\nu(\bar{u}) \subseteq \{x\}$ and $\nu(\bar{v}) \subseteq \{y\}$. Since $\nu(\bar{u}) \cap \nu(\bar{v}) \neq \emptyset$, $\nu(\bar{u}) = \{x\} = \nu(\bar{v})$. Therefore, (9) holds for H_2 .

CT'₀ \implies **WCT₀**: Obvious.

The remaining implications follow by transitivity. \square

Surprisingly, computable T_1 is the same as computable T_2 . The hierarchy between **WCT₀** and **SCT₂** collapses for spaces without isolated points.

Corollary 6. *If $\{x\}$ is not open for all $x \in X$ then **WCT₀** \implies **SCT₂***

Proof: If $\{x\}$ is not open for all $x \in X$ then **WCT₀** is equivalent to **SCT₂**. \square

The space $\mathbf{R}_{<}$ from Example 1.2 is not T_2 since every pair of non-empty open sets has non-empty intersection. By Corollary 6 the space $\mathbf{R}_{<}$ is not even WCT_0 . The outer representation $\delta^- : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow X$ of points is defined by $\delta^-(p) = x \iff \theta(p) = X \setminus \overline{\{x\}}$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 5]. The 2nd statement below has been proved in [Xu and Grubba 2009] for spaces with non-empty base elements.

Theorem 7. *For computable topological spaces \mathbf{X} ,*

1. \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 , if \mathbf{X} is T_2 and $\{(u, v) \mid \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset\}$ is r.e.,
2. \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 iff $x \neq y$ is (δ, δ) -r.e..
3. \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 iff $\delta \leq \delta^-$.

Proof:

1. Let $H := \{(u, v) \mid \nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset\}$.

2. \implies : By (10,11), for all $x, y \in X$, $x \neq y \iff (\exists(u, v) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge y \in \nu(v))$. Since “ $x \in \nu(u)$ ” is (δ, ν) -r.e. [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009], $x \neq y$ is (δ, δ) -r.e.

\impliedby : By [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Theorem 11] there is a computable function g such that $\bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \theta \circ g(w)$ for all $w \in \text{dom}(\nu^{\text{fs}})$. Suppose that $x \neq y$ is (δ, δ) -r.e. Then there is a machine M that halts on input $(p, q) \in \text{dom}(\delta) \times \text{dom}(\delta)$ iff $\delta(p) \neq \delta(q)$. There is a machine N that halts on input (u, v) iff $u, v \in \text{dom}(\nu)$ and there are $u_0, v_0 \in \text{dom}(\nu^{\text{fs}})$ such that M halts on input $(u_0 1^\omega, v_0 1^\omega)$ in at most $\min(|u_0|, |v_0|)$ steps and $u \ll g(u_0)$ and $v \ll g(v_0)$. Let $H := \text{dom}(f_N)$. We must show (10) and (11).

Suppose that $x \neq y$. There are p, q such that $x = \delta(p)$ and $y = \delta(q)$. Then M halts on input (p, q) , hence there are $u_0 \ll p$ and $v_0 \ll q$ such that M halts on input $(u_0 1^\omega, v_0 1^\omega)$ in at most $\min(|u_0|, |v_0|)$ steps. There are $u \ll g(u_0)$ and $v \ll g(v_0)$ such that $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$. By definition, N halts on input (u, v) . This proves (10).

Suppose $(u, v) \in H$. Then there are $u_0, v_0 \in \text{dom}(\nu^{\text{fs}})$ such that M halts on input $(u_0 1^\omega, v_0 1^\omega)$ in at most $\min(|u_0|, |v_0|)$ steps and $u \ll g(u_0)$ and $v \ll g(v_0)$.

If $\nu(u) = \emptyset$ or $\nu(v) = \emptyset$ then $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset$. Assume $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$. Then $x = \delta(u_0 p)$ and $y = \delta(v_0 q)$ for some $p, q \in \Sigma^\omega$. Since M must halt also on input $(u_0 p, v_0 q)$, $x \neq y$. Therefore $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \emptyset$. This proves (11).

3. For every open set W ,

$$W \cap B = \emptyset \iff W \cap \overline{B} = \emptyset. \quad (12)$$

Suppose SCT_2 . Since $\delta(p) \in \nu(u)$ is r.e. [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Theorem 13.1] and H is r.e. by assumption (Definition 3), there is a computable function $h : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^\omega$ such that for all $p \in \text{dom}(\delta)$, $v \ll h(p)$ iff $(\exists u) (\delta(p) \in \nu(u))$

and $(u, v) \in H$). Suppose $\delta(p) = x$. For every $y \neq x$ there is some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$. Therefore, $\theta \circ h(p) = X \setminus \{x\}$.

By (12), $\theta \circ h(p) \subseteq X \setminus \overline{\{x\}} \subseteq X \setminus \{x\} = \theta \circ h(p)$, hence $\delta^- \circ h(p) = x$. Therefore, the function h translates δ to δ^- .

On the other hand let h be a computable function translating from δ to δ^- . Let $\delta(p) = x$ and $\delta(q) = y$. Since \mathbf{X} is T_0 ,

$$x \neq y \iff (\exists W \in \tau)(x \in W \wedge y \notin W) \text{ or } (\exists W \in \tau)(x \notin W \wedge y \in W).$$

Since $y \notin W \iff W \subseteq X \setminus \overline{\{y\}}$ by (12), and $\delta^- \circ h(q) = y$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\exists W \in \tau)(x \in W \wedge y \notin W) &\iff (\exists W \in \tau)(x \in W \wedge W \subseteq X \setminus \overline{\{y\}}) \\ &\iff x \in X \setminus \overline{\{y\}} \\ &\iff \delta(p) \in \theta \circ h(q) \end{aligned},$$

and correspondingly $(\exists W \in \tau)(x \notin W \wedge y \in W) \iff \delta(q) \in \theta \circ h(p)$.

Since $x \in V$ is (δ, θ) -r.e. [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Corollary 14], there is a machine that halts on input (p, q) iff $\delta(p) \neq \delta(q)$. By (2) of this theorem, the space is SCT_2 . \square

5 Counterexamples

We show by counterexamples that a number of implications for the computable separation axioms for computable separable spaces are not true in general. A topological space is discrete iff every singleton $\{x\}$ is open iff every subset $B \subseteq X$ is open. Every discrete space is T_i for $i = 0, 1, 2$. Let “D” be the axiom stating that the topological space is discrete. In the following examples let $(a_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}, (b_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}, \dots, (e_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ be injective families with pairwise disjoint ranges and let $\{0, 1, \dots, 7\} \subseteq \Sigma$.

Example 2. (D but not WCT_0) Let $X := \{a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i, e_i \mid i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ and let τ be the discrete topology on X . For all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ let $\nu(0^i 5) = \{c_i\}$, $\nu(0^i 6) = \{d_i\}$, $\nu(0^i 7) = \{e_i\}$. Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be some non-r.e. set and define $\nu(0^i 1), \dots, \nu(0^i 4)$ by the following table.

	$\nu(0^i 1)$	$\nu(0^i 2)$	$\nu(0^i 3)$	$\nu(0^i 4)$
$i \in A$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	$\{c_i, d_i\}$	$\{d_i, e_i\}$
$i \notin A$	$\{c_i, d_i\}$	$\{d_i, e_i\}$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$

The function ν defined so far is a notation of a base of the discrete topology on X . In order to make intersection computable we extend ν by adding names of intersections for 2 and 3 different names defined so far. For all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ and all $k, l, m \in \{1, \dots, 7\}$ such that $k \neq l$, $k \neq m$ and $l \neq m$ let $\nu(0^i kl) := \nu(0^i k) \cap \nu(0^i l)$ and $\nu(0^i klm) := \nu(0^i k) \cap \nu(0^i l) \cap \nu(0^i m)$. Let $\beta := \text{range}(\nu)$. Since for each i the intersection of this kind of more than 3 elements can be reduced to the intersection of 3 elements, $\mathbf{X} := (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ is a computable topological space.

Suppose \mathbf{X} is WCT_0 . Let $H \subseteq \text{dom}(\nu) \times \text{dom}(\nu)$ be an r.e. set such that (2) and (3). By (2) for $i \in A$ there must be some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $a_i \in \nu(u)$

and $b_i \in \nu(v)$. Then $u = 0^i1$ and $v = 0^i2$, hence $(0^i1, 0^i2) \in H$. For $i \notin A$, $\nu(0^i1) = \{c_i, d_i\}$ and $\nu(0^i2) = \{d_i, e_i\}$. Since (3) is violated, $(0^i1, 0^i2) \notin H$. Therefore, $i \in A$ iff $(0^i1, 0^i2) \in H$. Since H is r.e., the set A must be r.e. Contradiction. \square

Example 3. ($D + WCT_0$ but not CT_0) Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be some non-r.e. set. Let $X := \{a_i, b_i \mid i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ and let τ be the discrete topology on X . Below we will define sets $B, C, D \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $\{A, B, C, D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{N} . Define a notation ν of a basis β of the topology as follows.

	0^i1	0^i2	0^i3	0^i12	0^i13	0^i23
$i \in A \cup D$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset
$i \in B$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{a_i, b_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	$\{a_i\}$	\emptyset	$\{b_i\}$
$i \in C$	$\{a_i, b_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	$\{a_i\}$	\emptyset

Then $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) = \nu \circ g(u, v)$ for some computable function g , since $\nu(0^ik) \cap \nu(0^im) = \nu(0^ikm)$ for $k \neq m$. Therefore $\mathbf{X} := (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ is a computable topological space. Let $H := \{(0^ik, 0^jl) \mid i, j \in \mathbb{N}; k, l \in \{1, 2\}; (i \neq j \vee k \neq l)\}$. Then H satisfies (2) and (3) for the space \mathbf{X} . Therefore, \mathbf{X} is a WCT_0 -space.

We will define B and C such that \mathbf{X} is not SCT_0 . Let $l, r \in \Sigma^*$ such that $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(l) = 1$ and $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(r) = 2$. We assume w.l.o.g. that $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}$ is injective. For $i \in \mathbb{N}$ let

$$S_i := \{\langle l, 0^i1 \rangle, \langle r, 0^i3 \rangle, \langle l, 0^i12 \rangle, \langle r, 0^i23 \rangle\},$$

$$T_i := \{\langle r, 0^i2 \rangle, \langle l, 0^i3 \rangle, \langle r, 0^i12 \rangle, \langle l, 0^i13 \rangle\}.$$

Suppose, the function $f : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \times \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ realizes the separation function t_0^s for \mathbf{X} . If $\delta(p) = a_i$ and $\delta(q) = b_i$ then

$$f(p, q) \in \begin{cases} S_i & \text{if } i \in B \\ T_i & \text{if } i \in C \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

since $\nu(u)$ must be either $\{a_i\}$ or $\{b_i\}$ if $f(p, q) = \langle w, u \rangle$. Notice that $S_i \cap T_i = \emptyset$.

For all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ define $p_i, q_i \in \Sigma^\omega$ by $p_i := \iota(0^i1)\iota(0^i1)\iota(0^i1)\dots$ and $q_i := \iota(0^i2)\iota(0^i2)\iota(0^i2)\dots$. Let F be the set of all computable functions $f : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \times \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ such that $f(p_i, q_i)$ exists for all $i \in A$. Consider $f \in F$. Then $f' : i \mapsto f(p_i, q_i)$ is computable such that $A \subseteq \text{dom}(f')$. Since A is not r.e. and $\text{dom}(f')$ is r.e., $\text{dom}(f') \setminus A$ is infinite. Since F is countable, there is a bijective function $g : E \rightarrow F$ for some $E \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $i \in \text{dom}(g'_i) \setminus A$ for all $i \in E$ ($g_i := g(i)$). Then $A \cap E = \emptyset$. Notice that $g_i(p_i, q_i)$ exists for all $i \in E$.

For each $i \in E$ we put i to B or C in such a way that g_i does not realize the separating function t_0^s for SCT_0 . Let

$$B := \{i \in E \mid g_i(p_i, q_i) \notin S_i\},$$

$$C := \{i \in E \mid g_i(p_i, q_i) \in S_i\}, \quad (14)$$

and $D := \mathbb{N} \setminus (A \cup B \cup C)$. Since $A \cap E = \emptyset$, $E = B \cup C$ and $B \cap C = \emptyset$, $\{A, B, C, D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{N} .

Suppose some computable function f realizes t_0^s . Since $\delta(p_i) = a_i$ and $\delta(q_i) = b_i$ for $i \in A$, $f(p_i, q_i)$ exists for all $i \in A$, hence $f = g_i$ for some $i \in E$.

Since g_i realizes t_0^s , $g_i(p_i, q_i) \in S_i \iff i \in B$ by (13). On the other hand, $g_i(p_i, q_i) \in S_i \iff i \notin B$ by the definition of B (14). From this contradiction we conclude that \mathbf{X} is not SCT_0 . By Theorem 5, \mathbf{X} is not CT_0 . \square

Example 4. (D and CT_0 but not CT_1) Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be some non-r.e. set. Let $X := \{a_i, b_i \mid i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ and let τ be the discrete topology on X . Below we will define sets $B, C, D \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $\{A, B, C, D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{N} . For $i \in \mathbb{N}$ define $\nu(0^i1), \dots, \nu(0^i4)$ as follows.

	0^i1	0^i2	0^i3	0^i4
$i \in A \cup D$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	\emptyset	\emptyset
$i \in B$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{a_i, b_i\}$	\emptyset	$\{b_i\}$
$i \in C$	$\{a_i\}$	$\{a_i, b_i\}$	$\{b_i\}$	\emptyset

For $k, m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $k \neq m$, define $\nu(0^i km) := \nu(0^i k) \cap \nu(0^i m)$. Let $\beta := \text{range}(\nu)$. Since for each i and pairwise different k, l, m , $\nu(0^i k) \cap \nu(0^i l) \cap \nu(0^i m) = \emptyset$, $\mathbf{X} := (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ is a computable topological space. Let $P_i := \{0^i k, 0^i kl \mid k, l \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}\}$. If $\delta(p) = x$, then $x \in \{a_i, b_i\}$ for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$, hence $u \in P_i$ for all $u \ll p$, since by definition $u \ll p \iff x \in \nu(u)$.

We show that the space \mathbf{X} is CT_0 . There is a machine that on input $p, q \in \Sigma^\omega$ searches for words $u \ll p$ and $v \ll q$. If $u, v \in P_i$ for some i then the machine writes 0^i1 , if $u \in P_i$ and $v \in P_j$ for some $i \neq j$, then it writes u . Suppose $\delta(p) \neq \delta(q)$.

Case: $u, v \in P_i$ for some i : Then $\{\delta(p), \delta(q)\} = \{a_i, b_i\}$, hence $\delta(p) \in \nu(0^i1) = \{a_i\}$ or $\delta(q) \in \nu(0^i1) = \{a_i\}$. Therefore, $(\delta(p) \in \nu(u)$ and $\delta(q) \notin \nu(u))$ or $(\delta(p) \notin \nu(u)$ and $\delta(q) \in \nu(u))$.

Case: $u \in P_i$ and $v \in P_j$ for some $i \neq j$: Then $\delta(p) \in \nu(u) \subseteq \{a_i, b_i\}$ and $\delta(q) \in \nu(v) \subseteq \{a_j, b_j\}$. Therefore, $\delta(p) \in \nu(u)$ and $\delta(q) \notin \nu(u)$.

In summary, \mathbf{X} is CT_0 .

We show that \mathbf{X} is not CT_2 . For all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ define $p_i, q_i \in \Sigma^\omega$ by

$$\begin{aligned} p_i &:= \iota(0^i1)\iota(0^i1)\iota(0^i1)\dots \\ q_i &:= \iota(0^i2)\iota(0^i2)\iota(0^i2)\dots \end{aligned}$$

Let F be the set of all computable functions $f : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \times \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ such that $f(p_i, q_i)$ exists for all $i \in A$. Consider $f \in F$. Then $f' : i \mapsto f(p_i, q_i)$ is computable such that $A \subseteq \text{dom}(f')$. Since A is not r.e. and $\text{dom}(f')$ is r.e., $\text{dom}(f') \setminus A$ is

infinite. Since F is countable, there is a bijective function $g : E \rightarrow F$ for some $E \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $i \in \text{dom}(g'_i) \setminus A$ for all $i \in E$ ($g_i := g(i)$). Then $A \cap E = \emptyset$ and $g_i(p_i, q_i) \in \Sigma^*$ exists for all $i \in E$.

For each $i \in E$ we put i to B or C in such a way that g_i does not realize the separating function t_2 for CT_2 . For $i \in E$ let

$$i \in B : \iff \neg(\exists u \in \Sigma^*, v \in \{0^i4, 0^i24\})g_i(p_i, q_i) = \langle u, v \rangle, \quad (15)$$

$C := E \setminus B$ and $D := \mathbb{N} \setminus (A \cup B \cup C)$. Then $\{A, B, C, D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{N} .

Suppose there is some computable function f that realizes the separating function t_2 for CT_2 . Since $\delta(p_i) = a_i$ and $\delta(q_i) = b_i$ for $i \in A$, $f(p_i, q_i)$ exists for all $i \in A$. Therefore, $f = g_i$ for some $i \in E$, hence $g_i(p_i, q_i)$ exists.

There are $w_1, w_2 \in \Sigma^*$ such that $g_i(p_i, q_i) = g_i(w_1p, w_2q)$ for all $p, q \in \Sigma^\omega$.

Suppose $i \in B$. There are p, q such that $\delta(w_1p) = a_i$ and $\delta(w_2q) = b_i$. Since $f = g_i$ realizes t_2 , there are $u, v \in \Sigma^*$ such that $g_i(p_i, q_i) = g_i(w_1p, w_2q) = \langle u, v \rangle$ and $\nu(v) = \{b_i\}$, hence $v \in \{0^i4, 0^i24\}$. But then $i \notin B$ by (15). Contradiction.

Suppose $i \in C = E \setminus B$. Again there are p, q such that $\delta(w_1p) = a_i$ and $\delta(w_2q) = b_i$. Also, since $f = g_i$ realizes t_2 , there are $u, v \in \Sigma^*$ such that $g_i(p_i, q_i) = g_i(w_1p, w_2q) = \langle u, v \rangle$ and $\nu(v) = \{b_i\}$, hence $v \in \{0^i3, 0^i23\}$. But then $i \in B$ by (15). Contradiction.

From this contradiction we conclude that \mathbf{X} is not CT_2 . By Theorem 5, \mathbf{X} is not CT_1 . \square

Example 5. (D and CT_2 but not SCT_2) Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be an r.e. set with non-r.e. complement. Define a notation ν by

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(0^i1) &:= \{a_i\}, \nu(0^i2) := \{a_i\} \text{ for } i \in A, \\ \nu(0^i1) &:= \{a_i\}, \nu(0^i2) := \{b_i\} \text{ for } i \notin A \end{aligned}$$

for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Then ν is a notation of a base β of a topology (the discrete topology) τ on a subset $X \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ is a computable topological space.

The space \mathbf{X} is T_2 since it is discrete. It is CT_2 but not SCT_2 : The set $H := \{(0^ik, 0^jl) \mid i, j \in \mathbb{N}, k, l \in \{1, 2\}\}$ satisfies CT'_2 . By Theorem 5 the space is CT_2 . Suppose SCT_2 . Let H be the r.e. set for SCT_2 . By (10), $i \notin A \implies (0^i1, 0^i2) \in H$ and by (11), $i \in A \implies (0^i1, 0^i2) \notin H$. Since H is r.e., the complement of A must be r.e. (contradiction). Notice that $x \neq y$ is not (δ, δ) -r.e., see Theorem 7.2. \square

We summarize the counterexamples as follows.

Theorem 8. For computable topological spaces,

$$T_0 \not\Rightarrow WCT_0 \quad (\text{Example 1.2}) \quad (16)$$

$$T_1 \not\Rightarrow WCT_0 \quad (\text{Example 1.4}) \quad (17)$$

$$D \not\Rightarrow WCT_0 \quad (\text{Example 2;}) \quad (18)$$

$$D + WCT_0 \not\Rightarrow CT_0 \quad (\text{Example 3}) \quad (19)$$

$$D + CT_0 \not\Rightarrow CT_1 \quad (\text{Example 4}) \quad (20)$$

$$D + CT_2 \not\Rightarrow SCT_2 \quad (\text{Example 5}) \quad (21)$$

Since $D \Rightarrow T_2 \Rightarrow T_1 \Rightarrow T_0$, (16), (17) as well as $T_2 \not\Rightarrow CT_2$ follow from (18) by Theorem 5. Further results can be obtained in the same way.

Figure 1: The relation between computable T_0 -, T_1 -, and T_2 -separation.

Figure 1 visualizes the relations between the computable versions of T_i for $i = 0, 1, 2$ from Definitions 2 and 3 we have proved. “ $A \rightarrow B$ ” means $A \Rightarrow B$, “ $A \not\rightarrow B$ ” means that we have constructed a computable topological space for which $A \wedge \neg B$, and “ $A \not\rightarrow^C B$ ” means that we have constructed a computable topological space for which $(A \wedge C) \wedge \neg B$. Remember that $SCT_0 \Leftrightarrow CT_0 \Leftrightarrow CT'_0$ and $CT_1 \Leftrightarrow CT'_1 \Leftrightarrow CT_2 \Leftrightarrow CT'_2$.

6 Separation of Compact Sets and Intuitionistic Separation

In a Hausdorff space not only different points but also disjoint compact sets can be separated by open neighborhoods [Engelking 1989]. For each of the axioms CT_2 and SCT_2 we introduce generalizations for separating points and compact sets and for separating compact sets and compact sets.

Definition 9.

CT_2^{PC} : The multi-function t^{PC} is $(\delta, \kappa, [\nu, \bigcup \nu^{fs}])$ -computable, where t^{PC} maps

every $x \in X$ and every compact K such that $x \notin K$ to some pair (U, W) of disjoint open sets such that $x \in U$ and $K \subseteq W$.

CT_2^{cc} : The multi-function t^{cc} is $(\kappa, \kappa, [\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}, \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}])$ -computable, where t^{cc} maps every disjoint pair (K, L) of non-empty compact sets to some pair (V, W) of disjoint open sets such that $K \subseteq V$ and $L \subseteq W$.

SCT_2^{pc} : There is an r.e. set $H \in \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\forall x \in X)(\forall \text{ compact } K) \text{ such that } x \notin K \\ (\exists (u, w) \in H)(x \in \nu(u) \wedge K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w)) \end{array} \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad (22)$$

$$(\forall (u, w) \in H) \nu(u) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \emptyset. \quad (23)$$

SCT_2^{cc} : There is an r.e. set $H \in \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\forall \text{ compact } K, L) \text{ such that } K \cap L = \emptyset \\ (\exists (u, v) \in H)(K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u) \wedge L \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)) \end{array} \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad (24)$$

$$(\forall (u, v) \in H) \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v) = \emptyset. \quad (25)$$

For the above computable separation axioms the notation ν of the base and the notation $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}$ of the finite unions of base elements can be replaced by the representation θ of the open sets, and the axioms are robust, that is, they do not depend on the notation ν of the base explicitly but only on the computability concept on the points induced by it [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 21, Theorem 22].

Lemma 10. 1. Let $\overline{\text{CT}}_2^{\text{pc}}$ and $\overline{\text{CT}}_2^{\text{cc}}$ be the conditions obtained from CT_2^{pc} and CT_2^{cc} , respectively, by replacing ν and $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}$ by θ . Then $\overline{\text{CT}}_2^{\text{pc}} \iff \text{CT}_2^{\text{pc}}$ and $\overline{\text{CT}}_2^{\text{cc}} \iff \text{CT}_2^{\text{cc}}$

2. Let $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = (X, \tau, \tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\nu})$ be a computable topological space equivalent to $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 21]. Then the separation axioms SCT_2^{pc} and SCT_2^{cc} for \mathbf{X} is equivalent to the corresponding axiom for $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$.

Proof: Straightforward, see the proof of Lemma 4. □

The computable T_2 axioms are related as follows:

Theorem 11.

$$1. \text{SCT}_2^{\text{cc}} \iff \text{SCT}_2^{\text{pc}} \iff \text{SCT}_2 \implies \text{CT}_2^{\text{cc}} \implies \text{CT}_2^{\text{pc}} \implies \text{CT}_2$$

2. The space \mathbf{X} from Example 5 is CT_2 but not CT_2^{pc} .

Proof: 1. $\text{SCT}_2 \implies \text{SCT}_2^{\text{pc}}$: Since intersection on open sets is computable [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Theorem 11], there is a computable function g such that $\theta \circ g(v) = \bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)$. Let $H \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ be the r.e. set satisfying (10)

and (11) from Definition 3. Let H' be the set of all $(u, w) \in \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ such that for some finite set $N \subseteq H$ and some word v , $\nu^{\text{fs}}(v) = \text{pr}_1 N$, $\nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \text{pr}_2 N$ and $u \ll g(v)$. The set H' is r.e. Suppose, K is compact and $x \notin K$. By (10) for each $y \in K$ there is some $(u', v') \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u')$, $y \in \nu(v')$ and $\nu(u') \cap \nu(v') = \emptyset$. Since K is compact, there are a finite subset $N \subseteq H$ of such pairs and words u, w such that $\nu^{\text{fs}}(v) = \text{pr}_1 N$, $\nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \text{pr}_2 N$, $x \in \bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)$ and $K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w)$. Finally, there is some u such that $x \in \nu(u)$ and $u \ll g(v)$. By definition, $(u, w) \in H'$. This proves (22).

Suppose $(u, w) \in H'$. Then there are some finite set $N \subseteq H$ and some word v such that $\nu^{\text{fs}}(v) = \text{pr}_1 N$, $\nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \text{pr}_2 N$ and $u \ll g(v)$. Since $\nu(u') \cap \nu(v') = \emptyset$ for all $(u', v') \in N$, $\bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}(v) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \emptyset$ and hence $\nu(u) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \emptyset$ since $\nu(u) \subseteq \bigcap \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)$. This proves (23)

SCT₂^{pc} \implies **SCT₂^{cc}** : There is a computable function f_1 such that $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(w) = \theta \circ f_1(w)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Lemma 10]. Then the function $f_2 : \iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n) \mapsto \langle 1^n, f_1(v_1), \dots, f_1(v_n) \rangle$ is computable. By [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Lemma 11.1] there is a computable function f_3 such that $\bigcap \theta^{\text{fs}}(q) = \theta \circ f_3(q)$. Therefore, for the computable function $f := f_3 \circ f_2$, $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_1) \cap \dots \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_n) = \theta \circ f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$.

Let $H \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ be the r.e. set satisfying (22) and (23) from Definition 9. Let H' be the set of all pairs (u, v) of words for which there are some n , and pairs $(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_n, v_n) \in H$ such that $u = \iota(u_1) \dots \iota(u_n)$ and v is a prefix of $f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$. We show that (24) and (25) are true for H' .

Let K, L be disjoint compact sets. Then by (22) for every $y \in K$ there is some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $y \in \nu(u)$ and $L \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)$. Since K is compact there are $(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_n, v_n) \in H$ such that $K \subseteq \nu(u_1) \cup \dots \cup \nu(u_n) = \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u)$ for $u = \iota(u_1) \dots \iota(u_n)$ and $L \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_1) \cap \dots \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_n) = \theta \circ f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$. Since L is compact there is some prefix v of $f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$ such that $L \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v) \subseteq f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$. Therefore, $(u, v) \in H'$, $K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u)$ and $L \in \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v)$. This proves (24).

Suppose, $(u, v) \in H'$. Then there are $(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_n, v_n) \in H$ such that $u = \iota(u_1) \dots \iota(u_n)$ and v is a prefix of $f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$. Then $(\nu(u_1) \cup \dots \cup \nu(u_n)) \cap (\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_1) \cap \dots \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_n)) = \emptyset$. Since $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u) = \nu(u_1) \cup \dots \cup \nu(u_n)$, $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_1) \cap \dots \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_n) = \theta \circ f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$ and v is a prefix of $f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$, $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v) \subseteq f(\iota(v_1) \dots \iota(v_n))$, hence $\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v) = \emptyset$. This proves (25).

SCT₂^{cc} \implies **SCT₂** : Let $H \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ be the r.e. set satisfying (24) and (25) from Definition 9. We observe that every singleton $\{x\}$ is compact and $\{x\} \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u)$ iff $x \in \nu(u')$ for some $u' \ll u$. Let H' be the set of all (u', v') such that $u' \ll u$ and $v' \ll v$ for some $(u, v) \in H$. The H' is r.e. and (22) and (23) are true for H' .

$\mathbf{SCT}_2^{\text{cc}} \implies \mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{cc}}$: A κ -name of a compact set K is a list of all $u \in \Sigma^*$ such that $K \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(u)$. Let $H \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ be the r.e. set satisfying (24) and (25). There is a machine M that on input (p, q) searches for $u, v \in \Sigma^*$ such that $u \ll p$, $v \ll q$ and $(u, v) \in H$. Then the function f_M realizes the function t^{cc} .

$\mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{cc}} \implies \mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{pc}}$: The function $x \mapsto \{x\}$ is (δ, κ) -computable and the multi-function $(x, U) \mapsto V$ mapping every $x \in X$ and $U \in \text{range}(\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}})$ such that $x \in U$ to some $V \in \beta$ such that $x \in V$ is $(\delta, \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}, \nu)$ -computable. The multi-function t^{pc} is obtained from t^{cc} by composition, hence it is computable.

$\mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{pc}} \implies \mathbf{CT}_2$: By the same argument as above.

2. Suppose, there is a machine M such that the function f_M realizes the function t^{pc} from Definition 9. For $i \in \mathbb{N}$ let $p_i := \iota(0^i 1) \iota(0^i 1) \dots$ and let q_i be a list of all $w \in \text{dom}(\bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}})$ such that $0^{i2} \ll w$. Then for all $i \notin A$, $\delta(p_i) = a_i$ and $\kappa(q_i) = \{b_i\}$, hence $f_M(p_i, q_i) = \langle 0^i 1, v_i \rangle$ for some v_i such that $0^{i2} \ll v_i$ (such that $\{b_i\} \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_i)$). Let C be the set of all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $f_M(p_i, q_i) = \langle 0^i 1, v_i \rangle$ for some v_i such that $0^{i2} \ll v_i$. Since C is r.e. and $A^c \subseteq C$ there is some $k \in C \cap A$. Let t be the number of steps the machine M operates on input (p_k, q_k) until it halts. Let w be the prefix of q_i of length t . There is some $q' \in \Sigma^\omega$ such that $\kappa(wq') = \emptyset$. Also on input (p_k, wq') the machine will halt in t steps after writing $\langle 0^k 1, v_k \rangle$ such that $0^{k2} \ll v_k$. Since $k \in A$, $\{a_k\} = \nu(0^k 2) \subseteq \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_k)$. But $\nu(0^k 1) \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_k) = \{a_k\} \cap \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}}(v_k)$ should be empty, since $\{a_k\} = \delta(p_k) \notin \kappa(wq')$. Contradiction. Therefore, the space \mathbf{X} is not $\mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{pc}}$. \square

In [Xu and Grubba 2009] $\mathbf{SCT}_2 \implies (\mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{cc}} \wedge \mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{pc}} \wedge \mathbf{CT}_2)$ has been proved under the (unnecessary) assumption $U \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \beta$. We do not know whether the two remaining implications $\mathbf{SCT}_2 \implies \mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{cc}}$ and $\mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{cc}} \implies \mathbf{CT}_2^{\text{pc}}$ are proper.

Axioms of separation are studied also in Intuitionistic Analysis [Troelstra 1966] and Constructive Analysis [Bishop and Bridges 1985]. In [Waalwijk 1996, Page 50] a topological space is called *effective* iff

$$(\forall x \in X)(\forall U, x \in U)(\forall y \in X)[y \in U \vee (\exists V)(x \in V \wedge y \notin V)].$$

In our framework this axiom corresponds to:

Definition 12.

IT: The multi-function t mapping every $x, y \in X$ and $U \in \beta$ such that $x \in U$ to $(1, U)$ or to $(2, V)$ for some $V \in \beta$ such that $y \in U$ if the result is $(1, U)$ and $(x \in V \wedge y \notin V)$ if the result is $(2, V)$ is computable (more precisely, $(\delta, \delta, \nu, [\nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \nu])$ -computable).

Theorem 13. IT \iff \mathbf{SCT}_2

The proof is given in the next section.

7 Subspaces and Product Spaces

For a computable topological space $\mathbf{X} = (X, \tau, \beta, \nu)$ and $B \subseteq X$ the subspace $\mathbf{X}_B = (B, \tau_B, \beta_B, \nu_B)$ of \mathbf{X} to B is the computable topological space defined by $\text{dom}(\nu_B) := \text{dom}(\nu)$, $\nu_B(w) := \nu(w) \cap B$, see [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Section 8]. The separation axioms from Definitions 2 and 3 are invariant under restriction to subspaces.

Theorem 14. *If a computable topological space satisfies some separation axiom from Definitions 2, 3 and 9, then each subspace satisfies this axiom.*

Proof:

CT₀ : Suppose, there is a computable function $f : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \times \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ that maps every pair $(p, q) \in \text{dom}(\delta) \times \text{dom}(\delta)$ such that $\delta(p) \neq \delta(q)$ to some u such that $(\delta(p) \in \nu(u) \wedge \delta(q) \notin \nu(u))$ or $(\delta(p) \notin \nu(u) \wedge \delta(q) \in \nu(u))$. Suppose, $(p, q) \in \text{dom}(\delta_B) \times \text{dom}(\delta_B)$. Since $\delta(r) = \delta_B(r)$ for all $r \in \text{dom}(\delta_B)$, $f(p, q) = U$ such that $(\delta(p) \in \nu(u) \wedge \delta(q) \notin \nu(u))$ or $(\delta(p) \notin \nu(u) \wedge \delta(q) \in \nu(u))$. Since $\nu_B(w) := \nu(w) \cap B$, $(\delta_B(p) \in \nu_B(u) \wedge \delta_B(q) \notin \nu_B(u))$ or $(\delta_B(p) \notin \nu_B(u) \wedge \delta_B(q) \in \nu_B(u))$.

SCT₀, CT₁, CT₂ : Similar to **CT₀**.

WCT₀ : Suppose, the r.e. set H satisfies (2) and (3) for the space \mathbf{X} . By (2), for all $x, y \in B$ there is some $(u, v) \in H$ such that $x \in \nu(u)$ and $y \in \nu(v)$, hence $x \in \nu_B(u)$ and $y \in \nu_B(v)$. Therefore, (2) is true for \mathbf{X}_B . Suppose, $\nu_B(u) \cap \nu_B(v) \neq \emptyset$. then $\nu(u) \cap \nu(v) \cap B \neq \emptyset$. By (3) there is some $x \in X$ such that $\nu(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu(v)$ or some $y \in X$ such that $\nu(v) = \{y\} \subseteq \nu(u)$. In the first case, if $x \notin B$ then $\nu_B(u) = \nu(u) \cap B = \emptyset$ (contradiction), hence $x \in B$ and $\nu_B(u) = \{x\} \subseteq \nu_B(v)$. Correspondingly, in the second case $y \in B$ and $\nu_B(v) = \{y\} \subseteq \nu_B(u)$. Therefore, (3) is true for \mathbf{X}_B .

CT'₀, CT'₁, CT'₂, SCT'₂ : Similar to **WCT₀**.

CT₂^{pc}, CT₂^{sc} : This follows from [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Lemma 26] and the fact that $K \subseteq B$ is compact in \mathbf{X}_B iff it is compact in \mathbf{X} . \square

The product of two T_i -spaces is a T_i -space for $i = 0, 1, 2$. This is no longer true for some of the computable separation axioms. The product $\mathbf{X}_1 \times \mathbf{X}_2 = \overline{\mathbf{X}} = (X_1 \times X_2, \overline{\tau}, \overline{\beta}, \overline{\nu})$ of two *computable* topological spaces $\mathbf{X}_1 = (X_1, \tau_1, \beta_1, \nu_1)$ and $\mathbf{X}_2 = (X_2, \tau_2, \beta_2, \nu_2)$, is defined by $\overline{\nu}\langle u_1, u_2 \rangle = \nu_1(u_1) \times \nu_2(u_2)$ [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Section 8]. Let \mathbf{R} be the computable real line from Example 1.

Theorem 15.

1. *The SCT₂-spaces are closed under product.*
2. *If $\mathbf{X}_1 \times \mathbf{X}_2$ is SCT₂ and X_2 has a computable point, then X_1 is SCT₂.*

3. $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is WCT_0 iff \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 .
4. For every axiom T such that $SCT_2 \implies T \implies WCT_0$ the following statements are equivalent:
 - $T \iff SCT_2$,
 - the T -spaces are closed under product,
 - $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is a T -space for every T -space \mathbf{X} .
5. The WCT_0 -, CT_0 - CT_1 - and CT_2 -spaces are not closed under product.

Proof: 1. Suppose, \mathbf{X}_1 and \mathbf{X}_2 are SCT_2 . By Theorem 7, $x_i \neq y_i$ is (δ_i, δ_i) -r.e. for $i = 1, 2$, hence $(x_1, x_2) \neq (y_1, y_2)$ is $([\delta_1, \delta_2], [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ -r.e., hence again by Theorem 7, $\mathbf{X}_1 \times \mathbf{X}_2$ is SCT_2 .

2. Let $z = \delta_2(p')$ for some computable $p' \in \Sigma^\omega$. By Theorem 7.2, on $X_1 \times X_2$ the relation $(x_1, x_2) \neq (y_1, y_2)$ is $([\delta_1, \delta_2], [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ -r.e. Therefore, there is a machine M that halts on input $(\langle p_1, p' \rangle, \langle q_1, p' \rangle)$ for $p_1, q_1 \in \text{dom}(\delta_1)$ iff $\delta(p_1) \neq \delta(q_1)$. Since p' is computable, there is a machine N that halts on input (p_1, q_1) iff $\delta_1(p_1) \neq \delta_1(q_1)$, hence $x \neq y$ is (δ_1, δ_1) -r.e. By Theorem 7.2, \mathbf{X}_1 must be SCT_2 .

3. Suppose $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is WCT_0 . An open basis set of $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ has the form $U \times (a; b)$ with rational $a < b$. Therefore, no set $\{(x, y)\}$ for $(x, y) \in X \times R$ is open. By Corollary 6, $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is SCT_2 . By 2. of this theorem, \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 . Suppose \mathbf{X} is SCT_2 . Since \mathbf{R} is SCT_2 , $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is SCT_2 hence WCT_0 .

4. Suppose $T \iff SCT_2$. Then T -spaces are closed under product by 1. of this theorem. Then $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is a T -space for every T -space \mathbf{X} , since \mathbf{R} is an SCT_2 -space and hence a T -space. Suppose, $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{R}$ is a T -space for every T -space \mathbf{X} . Let \mathbf{Y} be a T -space. Then $\mathbf{Y} \times \mathbf{R}$ is a T -space, hence a WCT_0 -space. By 3. of this theorem, \mathbf{Y} is SCT_0 .

5. This follows from 4. of this theorem and Theorems 5 and 8. \square

Since we do not know whether $SCT_0 \iff CT_2^{\text{cc}}$ or $SCT_0 \iff CT_2^{\text{pc}}$, we do not know whether the CT_2^{cc} -spaces and the CT_2^{pc} -spaces are closed under product. Finally, we prove Theorem 13.

Proof: (Theorem 13) By Theorem 15.4, it suffices to prove $SCT_2 \implies IT \implies WCT_0$ and that the IT -spaces are closed under product.

$SCT_2 \implies IT$: Let H be the r.e. set from the Definition of SCT_2 in Definition 3. There is a machine M that on input (p, q, u) tries to show $u \ll q$ and simultaneously tries to find some $(v, w) \in H$ such that $v \ll p$ and $w \ll q$. If $u \ll q$ has been shown it writes $\langle w_1, u \rangle$, and if $(v, w) \in H$ has been found it writes $\langle w_2, v \rangle$ (where $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w_1) = 1$ and $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}(w_2) = 2$). Suppose, $\delta(p) = x \in U = \nu(u)$ and $\delta(q) = y$. The machine halts on input (p, q, u) , since $u \ll q$ can be proved if $x = y$, and some $(v, w) \in H$ can be found if $x \neq y$. If the result is $\langle w_1, u \rangle$ then $u \ll q$ hence $y \in U$. If the result is $\langle w_2, v \rangle$ then there is some w such that $(v, w) \in H$,

$x \in \nu(v)$ and $y \notin \nu(v)$. Therefore the machine realizes the multi-function t from Definition 12.

IT \implies CT₀ Since by our general assumption \mathbf{X} is a T_0 -space, for every $x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$ there is some $U \in \beta$ such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$ and $x \notin U$. There is a machine that on input (x, y) applies the multi-function t to (x, y, U) and to (y, x, U) in turn for all $U \in \beta$ until some $V \in \beta$ is found such that $((2, V) \in t(x, y, U)$ and $x \in V$) or $((2, V) \in t(y, x, U)$ and $y \in V$) and then gives V as its result. This machine computes the multifunction t_0 from Definition 2.

The IT-spaces are closed under product: Let $\mathbf{X}_1 = (X_1, \tau_1, \beta_1, \nu_1)$ and $\mathbf{X}_2 = (X_2, \tau_2, \beta_2, \nu_2)$ be IT-spaces. Suppose $(x_1, x_2) \in U_1 \times U_2$ and let $(y_1, y_2) \in X_1 \times X_2$ be another point. For $i = 1, 2$ there is a machine that on input (x_i, y_i, U_i) produces $(1, U_i)$ or $(2, V_i)$ such that $y_i \in U_i$ if the result is $(1, U_i)$ and $(x \in V_i \wedge y \notin V_i)$ if the result is $(2, V_i)$. Combining both machines we get a machine that on input $((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), U_1 \times U_2)$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} (1, U_1 \times U_2) & \text{ if the results are } (1, U_1) \text{ and } (1, U_2), \\ (2, V_1 \times U_2) & \text{ if the results are } (2, V_1) \text{ and } (1, U_2), \\ (2, U_1 \times V_2) & \text{ if the results are } (1, U_1) \text{ and } (2, V_2), \\ (2, V_1 \times V_2) & \text{ if the results are } (2, V_1) \text{ and } (2, V_2). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, this machine computes the multifunction t from Definition 12 for $\mathbf{X}_1 \times \mathbf{X}_2$. \square

8 Final Remarks

There may be other interesting axioms T of computable separation between WSCT_0 and SCT_2 . By Theorem 15 only the SCT_2 -spaces are closed under product and, hence, are the most natural ones. We do not know whether the implications $\text{CT}_2^{\text{pc}} \implies \text{CT}_2^{\text{cc}}$ and $\text{CT}_2^{\text{cc}} \implies \text{SCT}_2$ are proper. Several other axioms concerning compact sets instead of points have not been considered in this article, for example CT_1^{cp} : The multi-function mapping each *compact* set K and each *point* y such that $y \notin K$ to some open set V such that $K \subseteq V$ and $y \notin V$ is $(\kappa, \delta, \bigcup \nu^{\text{fs}})$ -computable.

The computable topology developed here and in [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009] is pointless topology. The “concrete objects” are the names of base elements ($\nu : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow \beta$) which are considered as “frames” or “regions” that can be filled with points. Names of other objects are composed from names of base elements (δ, θ, κ etc.) [Weihrauch and Grubba 2009, Definition 5, Section 10]. No axiom requires the existence of points, non-empty open sets etc., see Theorem 14.

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